

Horizon Europe Project PLANET4B

COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION STRATEGY (VERSION 2.0)

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

PLANET4B

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PLANET4B

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Key deliverable information

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Project coordination and scientific lead team	Ilkhom Soliev; Alex Franklin; Agnes Zolyomi; Torsten Wähler

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Corresponding author	Gyula Tóth
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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Definition
CAC	Climate Academy
CDE	Communication Dissemination and Exploitation
CG	CzechGlobe – Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences
CGE	Culture Goes Europe
COMCOM	Communication Committee of the project
CU	Coventry University
D	Deliverable
DC	Dadima's CIC
EO	Expected Outcome
ESSRG	Environmental Social Science Research Group
FiBL	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
FUG	Forum Urban Gardening
GA	Grant Agreement Project 101082212 – PLANET4B
GD	GoodIssue nonprofit Ltd. (GD)
IFZ	Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture
IPBES	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month (of the project time)
MLU	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg
NINA	Norwegian Institute for Nature Research
OOF	Greater Oslo Council for Outdoor Recreation
PCT	Project Coordination Team
PLANET4B	understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social IEarning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
PP	Project Partner
RU	Radboud University
TG1–6	Target group 1–6
UNEP-WCMC	UN Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre
UNIPI	University of Pisa
WP	Work Package

Table of contents

Key deliverable information	iii
List of abbreviations and acronyms	v
1. Executive summary	3
2. About the PLANET4B project	3
3. The Communication Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy	3
3.1 Introduction	3
3.2 Defining Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation	4
3.3 Objectives	5
3.4 Strategy and Planning	6
3.5 Summary of the first year	6
4. Target Audience and Messages	7
4.1 General Messages of the Project	7
4.2 Policymakers	8
4.3 Businesses	10
4.4 Civil Society	11
4.5 Scientific Community, Researchers	13
4.6 Youth, Educators and Social Movements	14
4.7 Local Communities	15
4.8 General Public	15
5. Communication and Dissemination Plan	16
5.1 Timeline of M19–M30	16
5.2 Project Partner’s Responsibilities and Workflow	21
6. Communication Channels and Tools	22
6.1 Visual Identity	22
6.2 Written Contents	23
6.3 Website	23
6.4 Social Media Channels	25
6.5 Newsletter	31
6.6 Briefs	31
6.7 Press Releases	31
6.8 Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications	32
6.9 Emails	32
6.10 Open-Source Platforms	32
6.11 Events	33

6.12 Consultations	33
6.13 Other Visual Tools.....	33
6.14 Media Relations	33
7. Synergies and Accelerating Changes.....	34
7.1 The Synergies Strategy	34
7.2 Channelling outcomes to accelerate change	34
8. Capacity Building for Enabling Players	35
9. Internal Communication	35
9.1. Internal Communication Rules and Tools	35
10. Exploitation.....	36
11. Monitoring Results.....	38

1. Executive summary

This document serves as the updated version of Deliverable 5.1 (D5.1) – the “Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) strategy” of Work Package 5 in the PLANET4B project. This revision reflects our learnings from the first year of the project and incorporates feedback from various project partners. The update aims to provide a concise summary of the project's progress, lessons learned, and lay down a strategic foundation for the remaining phases, focusing especially on building and expanding our base for the final stage when the main outcomes will be ready for launch.

2. About the PLANET4B project

We rely on biodiversity for our very existence – it provides us with the basic ecosystem services that allow us to survive and thrive. Still, human lives and the biosphere itself are under threat due to the loss of biodiversity occurring at a massive scale, and at an accelerating pace. Despite the mounting scientific evidence on the importance of biodiversity, it still takes a back seat to political and other agendas.

How can we change this alarming situation? The PLANET4B (understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making) research project aims to understand and influence decision making affecting biodiversity. The project's main objectives are: 1) to understand how factors such as gender, religion, ethnicity, race, age, culture, disability, norms, values and behaviour intersect and are implicated in biodiversity relevant decision making across a range of different scales and settings; and 2) to channel this understanding of complexity into the design of stakeholder interventions, transformative pathways and a series of targeted, yet scalable policy recommendations in order to prioritise biodiversity and halt biodiversity loss.

3. The Communication Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy

3.1 Introduction

This update is informed by our experiences and achievements in the first year, including our communication activities, internal meetings, and valuable feedback from our project partners. It aims to provide a snapshot of our progress, assess the effectiveness of our communication strategies and adapt our approach to better prepare for the concluding phase of the project, where we anticipate launching our main outcomes.

The process of updating the CDE plan involved retaining most of the original content, reflecting its ongoing relevance. To clearly indicate the updates, we have used the colour red. This approach serves a dual purpose: firstly, it emphasises that much of the original CDE plan remains pertinent and valid; secondly, the use of a different colour for modifications allows readers to easily identify changes while understanding them in the context of the existing plan.

Key changes include:

- 3.1 Introduction: An extra paragraph has been added to reflect our learned experiences.
- 3.5 Summary of the First Year: A new section has been introduced, providing a concise overview of the first year's progress and insights.
- 5.1 Timeline of the Second Phase: This section was revised to include updated outputs, tools, and actions planned for the next phase.
- 6.4 Social Media Channels: This part has been updated with strategies and suggestions aimed at improving the project's outreach through its social media channels.

These updates aim to effectively communicate the adjustments made in the plan, highlighting the continuity from the original strategy while incorporating new insights and strategies.

There are two major communication challenges the project faces. Probably the most significant one is that the communication sphere is overcrowded. The project's target audience are constantly overwhelmed with information. The other challenge is that PLANET4B is a (technical) research project but one of its main aims is to influence decision makers (to generate transformative change), who are often hard to reach. Both challenges can be addressed in several ways to have more significant impact, or more engagement with decision-makers.

To stand out and optimise the impact of PLANET4B – with the help of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy – the project will develop clear, understandable, targeted and co-created messages to the target groups, while also presenting key results in both structurally and visually engaging ways. The main objective of the communication activities is to increase the visibility of the project and its results ensuring that the scientific work is effectively communicated. The communication activities will go beyond reaching and engaging with the key target groups (policymakers, businesses, civil society, scientific community, youth and educators), and will also focus on local communities and stakeholders of the project's case studies, and on the general public.

Central to the communication activities is content creation, which will be built on the close cooperation among the PPs. These contents will be related to e.g. how we perceive biodiversity, what research results are there on how we make relevant decision making or how local stakeholders can build transformative pathways. As one of the central aspects of the project is to understand how intersectional characteristics define decision making, careful consideration of different cultural and social contexts will be made during the project's communication and dissemination activities.

3.2 Defining Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

Using the EU's definition¹ (in relation to Horizon Europe projects): communication is "reaching out to society and showing the impact and benefits of EU-funded activities",

¹ For all citations in this chapter see European IT Helpdesk (2022) as the relevant reference: European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, Scherer, J., Weber, S., Alveen, P., et al. (2022). European IP Helpdesk. Successful valorisation of knowledge and research

whereas communication activities, within the frame of EU projects are to “inform about and promote the project and its results, success in a non-technical manner.” Dissemination, on the other hand, focuses on the public disclosure of results, enabling others (policy makers, researchers, etc.) to use or re-use or internalise results and thus maximise the impact of EU-funded research.

However, communication and dissemination activities are intertwined and therefore cannot always be clearly distinguished from each other. “The boundaries between certain activities – in particular regarding communication actions and dissemination – are often blurry or can sometimes overlap. For instance, a magazine article highlighting the project’s work and achievements that is written for communication purposes could end up in the hands of potential stakeholders outside the project and trigger interest in using some of the results. The initial communication activity has now become a dissemination tool as well.”²

3.3 Objectives

The main purpose of this document is to provide a clear definition and explanation of the various communication instruments as well as the target audience and strategies in formulating messages. This will help PPs communicate more effectively and ensure that their efforts are aligned with achieving the project goals. Additionally, the CDE strategy and the annual CDE plan clearly outline the roles and responsibilities of each partner in executing different communication and dissemination activities. By establishing clear accountability, the plan aims to optimise communication efforts and maximise their impact on the intended audience. The CDE strategy and plan will also ensure that relevant actions address the key target groups with tailored messages through the relevant channels and in the most appropriate formats.

The overarching goal of the communication and dissemination activities is to initiate, accelerate and upscale biodiversity-relevant transformative changes in our society by disseminating the project results to researchers, scientific and policy-making institutions and networks, the related target groups and the general public. In addition, these activities aim to increase the visibility of the project and its results, ensuring that the scientific work is effectively communicated (and to understand how to communicate biodiversity more effectively). The activities defined in the plan are designed to raise awareness and maximise the impact of the project outputs.

Based on the experiences gleaned during the project's initial years, the CDE strategy is scheduled for another comprehensive update at M35. We are committed to a regular monitoring and revision process, occurring every six months, to ensure our strategy remains effective and responsive to the evolving needs of the project. This continual

results in Horizon Europe. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation. Ingbert, Publications Office of the European Union. Available from: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/437645>. Access: April 24th, 2023.

² For all citations in this chapter see European IP Helpdesk (2022) as the relevant reference: European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, Scherer, J., Weber, S., Alveen, P., et al. (2022). European IP Helpdesk. Successful valorisation of knowledge and research results in Horizon Europe. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation. Ingbert, Publications Office of the European Union. Available from: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/437645>. Access: April 24th, 2023.

refinement process allows us to adapt our approach effectively and align it with the progress and learnings from the project.

3.4 Strategy and Planning

This CDE strategy is designed to help the PPs communicate effectively to achieve the project's objectives. This document defines the strategy's objectives (why we want to do it), the target audience (for whom), the messages (what we want to say), the channels (how we want to say it) and the actions (what we want to do). In other words: the CDE strategy aims to identify who needs to be reached and in what way, and when the target groups need to be addressed to successfully achieve a more substantial impact.

For the upcoming period, WP5 leader Good Issue (GD) will provide the internal planning for M19–M30 (see updated Table 9), ensuring a distribution of communication and dissemination tasks among PPs. This Communication and Dissemination strategy works as a detailed roadmap to organise the communication work according to timeline, needs and resources. While the strategy focuses on “what to do”, the plan instructs “how to do it” providing guidance on how to implement the strategy. The plan is specific, time-bound, and is developed regularly. Meanwhile, the strategy is set for its next update in M35 and is submitted as a separate deliverable.

3.5 Summary of the first year

In the first year of the PLANET4B project, we have witnessed significant progress alongside various challenges in our communication endeavours. Our experience shows that while our activities have successfully attracted attention with notable achievements like website visitors reaching over half of our targeted goal, and social media engagement demonstrating encouraging growth, there remain areas for improvement. We've identified challenges in maximising engagement and effectively disseminating information to our diverse target groups. These insights have been instrumental in shaping the updates to our Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation strategy, guiding us to focus on enhanced partner involvement, innovative content creation, and broader dissemination strategies for the project's crucial final phase.

In terms of concrete achievements and measurable outcomes, we have successfully met, and in some cases surpassed our initial targets. We aimed, for example, for five press releases and with the contribution of our project partners, have successfully achieved this goal. Exceeding the initial targets, the project was already presented at 20+ scientific events by the project partners. In line with our schedule, we distributed two newsletters. The project also gained media attention with a radio interview, further enhancing our visibility. 20 interview videos are in production right now, which is in line with our objective of creating 10 videos and illustrations throughout the entire project.

For a quick overview of the Key Performance Indicators, see Table 12. It should be noted that the figures will be refined in the mid-term report with the help of monitoring tables.

4. Target Audience and Messages

4.1 General Messages of the Project

In respect of interacting with the target audience and motivating it to act, clearly defined messages are crucial. Messages articulate and encapsulate what the project is about, but more importantly why it is vital and relevant for the target groups. Messages should convey responses to: Why should they be interested in the project/results? How could they benefit from the results of the project? What do we offer to them? What do we want them to do?

Relevant messages can (and should) be used in every project activity, whether a partner is posting on social media, presenting at a conference, writing the summary of a report or talking to a journalist. Messages can help partners to improve communication, to influence decision making and to achieve impact.

The following table (Table 1) includes examples for general messages, relating to the topics of the project, to aspects of credibility (e.g. to gain trust) as well as to aspects of novelty of the project’s work.

Table 1. Main general messages of the project. Source: Authors’ own work.

Category	Message
Topic-related (biodiversity, decision making, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss threatens our existence. Yet, this crisis is only getting worse showing inapt governance. • Our current socio-economic system built on consumption and overexploitation stands against nature and biodiversity (and us). • To affectively address this system and trigger transformation, we need to better understand why biodiversity is not prioritised at the first place. • Within PLANET4B, we will investigate why we do not already prioritise biodiversity and nature although we all find it important. • We will assess governing norms, values and belief systems as well as intersectionality aspects (e.g. gender, age, race, religion). • We will use transdisciplinary research and practices from economy through conservation to arts to analyse how we can make biodiversity more of a priority at the individual, community and institutional level. • We will provide practical guidance for policymakers, civil society members and businesses about how they can change minds and make better decisions for biodiversity saving the planet. • We will assess how religion, age, gender, disability and race may influence decision making on prioritising biodiversity through 11 case studies from eight countries. • We will assess how various sectors (education, fashion industry, finance, agriculture, trade) can reduce individual and institutional barriers to upscale biodiversity decision making. • We will attempt to understand how the locally gained knowledge can be built into the global level influencing major policies. • We will bridge a knowledge gap about understanding how biodiversity can be prioritised in individual and policy decision making. • The PLANET4B project deals with the globally relevant topic of biodiversity loss that affects all humankind and has consequences for our future and survival (keywords: our existence, crucial, survival, alarming, biodiversity loss, etc.).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project tries to understand how we can make decision making prioritise biodiversity more. • The project supports transformative actions for biodiversity.
Credibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The PLANET4B project is a cooperation between 16 partners from 10 countries: renowned universities, NGOs and SMEs, from all around Europe. • More than 60 researchers and experts are working on the outcomes.
Novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PLANET4B performs unique research on the topic. • Thanks to the consortium's wide transdisciplinary composition, the project can integrate knowledge from different disciplines (including political sciences, economics, sociology, psychology and communication sciences) as well as build on policy and practical knowledge. • The project compiles a much-needed gap-filling knowledge resource. • The project's research process is transdisciplinary, creative, action-oriented and participatory. • The findings will be synthesised and scaled up to EU and global levels. • The project hopes to trigger transformative change so biodiversity can be prioritised in decision making.

The target groups of the project are:

- Policymakers
- Businesses
- Civil society
- Scientific community
- Local communities
- Youth, educators and social movements
- General public

Before dissemination activities can be realised, certain questions need to be clarified to better understand and address the specific target group: What do we know about them? (What are their needs, news/information consuming habits?) What do we want to say/offer to them? How can we help them? What do we want them to do? What is their role in the solution?

4.2 Policymakers

One of the most influential actors to trigger transformative change may be relevant policymakers. To prioritise biodiversity and halt biodiversity loss, the co-produced knowledge of the project will be channelled into targeted, yet scalable policy recommendations. The project participants will ensure that the co-produced knowledge reaches the policymakers at the public and private levels, and that relevant knowledge is considered in policymaking. As a result of the dissemination, policymakers will understand better the importance of biodiversity, their role in transformation changes, the integration option of biodiversity to policy, the various factors defining decision making and the relevant institutional barriers and enablers. They will be able to make more effective biodiversity policy implementation, better policy formulation and prioritisation of biodiversity as well as better consideration of biodiversity in implementation. In addition, they will not only have a better understanding of the reviews and evaluation of policies but also integrate biodiversity into sectoral policy

transitions. Furthermore, the dissemination of results will ensure policy coherence with international processes and aid plausible policy transitions.

The policymakers will be reached mainly through bilateral policy consultations and policy events as well as via the project’s social media channels, using news, posts, briefs, illustrated transitional stories and policy reports. There will be three workshops with EU policymakers (e.g. DG ENG, DG AGRI, DG CLIMA). These workshops and consultations will take place in-person in Brussels or at relevant international events organised by the PPs with a maximum of 20 representatives/participants from the target groups per workshop. The workshops will build on (and integrate the results of) the specific case studies from WP3. Sectoral specific policy recommendations (agriculture, trade, finance, industry, education) about how transition can be upscaled to the EU and global levels will be communicated through 10 consultations with key enablers. Collaborating with relevant UN bodies (e.g. UNEP, UNDP, UN Women) will further ensure relevant messages are received by target groups and policy processes. The recommendations for EU and international policies (about how behavioural and intersectionality insights can aid policy coherence and implementation and how biodiversity can be further prioritised) will reach 100 enabling players using a synthesis policy report.

The following table (Table 2) includes specific messages for policymakers, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 2. Specific messages for policymakers Source: Authors’ own work.

Category	Message
<p>What do we offer them?</p> <p>Why should they be interested in the project/results?</p> <p>How could they benefit from the results of the project?</p> <p>What do we want them to do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using the PLANET4B outcomes policymakers can communicate better about biodiversity issues. • Policymakers can make more effective policy formulation and implementation in relation to biodiversity. • Policymakers can integrate biodiversity consideration in policymaking. • The project results provide a deeper understanding of the motivation behind business, institutional and private decision making that helps to implement existing biodiversity related policies more effectively. • The project can aid understanding how policies can best have a positive impact on biodiversity. • The project reveals major causes of limited biodiversity prioritisation and provide enablers for transformative change to limit and ultimately, stop biodiversity change. • The project promotes biodiversity and nature-based solutions that contribute to the food, water and raw materials security. • Policymakers can find the field of cooperation with businesses, education, the scientific sector and civil society working on biodiversity topics from local to global levels.
<p>Relevant outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D4.1 – Entry points for upscaling findings at relevant scales identified, based on consultations with key enabling players (EU policy makers and businesses). • D4.2 – Mapping of leverage points and transformative pathways for upscaling at the EU as well as global context, produced for five sectors (agriculture, finance, education, industry, trade). • D4.3 – Reports from workshops on validated methods and pathways at EU, global and sector level.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D4.4 – Knowledge products, including synthesis of the applicability of behaviour science and intersectionality for prioritising biodiversity into relevant EU and global processes. • D5.8 – Three comprehensive guidelines tailored for enabling players (civil society, policymakers and businesses).
Timeframe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuously, during the project • Intensive dissemination: M28–M36
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops • Meetings, bilateral consultations • Social media (LinkedIn, Twitter) • Newsletter • Conferences, events
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy report • Presentations • Briefs • Infographics • Illustrated transformative change stories

4.3 Businesses

Business decisions are crucial in preventing biodiversity loss as companies have a direct impact on the environment through their operations and supply chains. They can also influence consumer behaviour and policies through their actions and advocacy. To stop biodiversity loss, businesses can adopt sustainable sourcing, energy efficiency, corporate responsibility practices that prioritise sustainability and biodiversity, and advocate for policies that support conservation and sustainability. Overall, businesses have the power to impact biodiversity positively or negatively.

To engage financing and business leaders, the project will host a series of stakeholder workshops. Business entities can be reached through other activities, such as social media and presentations. These activities will build on (and integrate the results of) the specific case studies from WP3.

Examples of businesses, with which the consortium has established links, include Proteus Partnership, TNFD partners, Natural Capital organisations, World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD), Green Economy Coalition, EU Business@Biodiversity Platform.

The following table (Table 3) includes specific messages for businesses, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 3. Specific messages for businesses. Source: Authors' own work.

Category	Message
<p>What do we offer them?</p> <p>Why should they be interested in the project/results?</p> <p>How could they benefit from the results of the project?</p> <p>What do we want them to do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss is mainly triggered by the dominant global economic system – hence we need businesses to contribute to transformative changes. • Businesses contribute to biodiversity loss because of unsustainable practices, but with transformative changes and changing their values system, they can contribute to saving biodiversity and the society. • The current consumption practices have long-term destructive and detrimental effects on both nature and human health and well-being. • We need transformative change in the system to survive. • Making positive decisions for biodiversity businesses can answer the emerging “green” consumer needs better and reach a wider audience (consumers). • “More sustainable” businesses can make a significant impact. • They can manage and sustain their own resources better. • Transformative change can boost resilient production, higher quality of food, water and raw material security; understanding of new market demands; adaptation to climate change, early adaptation to future policies (fashion case study). • They can offer “greener” solutions to their respective market (finance case study). • They can diversify your portfolio.
Relevant outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.8 – Three comprehensive guidelines tailored for enabling players (civil society, policymakers and businesses). • WP3 outcomes, WP4 outcomes
Timeframe	From M6
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops and consultations • Social media • Newsletter • Media-news
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Briefs • Infographics • Illustrated transformative change stories

4.4 Civil Society

Civil society organisations (e.g. NGOs) play a crucial role in shaping the social, political and economic landscape of any society. One of the key reasons for their importance is their ability to reach and influence a broad segment of the population. Civil societies have existing channels, credibility and resources to engage with people from different backgrounds. Moreover, civil societies have further resources to reach a wide segment of society.

The project will provide guidance and support for target groups within the civil society sector to not only communicate better about biodiversity issues but also to be a catalyst for influencing policies to have greater societal impacts.

The project aims to reach three different groups that can be categorised under the term civil society:

- 1) Conservation NGOs working at EU and international levels (e.g. members of the European Habitats Forum including WWF, BirdLife, IUCN, Friends of the Earth, European Environmental Bureau, ClientEarth, OCEANA, FERN, Justice and Environment, Indigenous and Community Conserved Areas (ICCA), RARE, GreenPeace, etc.)
- 2) Social NGOs working on the local level with communities (consortium partners and their relevant networks – focusing on social issues such as gender, inclusion, diversity, migration, SDGs, etc.)
- 3) Organisations of sectoral groups – e.g. European Landowners Organisations (ELO), Copa Cogeca, International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM), Forestry and Trade Associations

The following table (Table 4) includes specific messages for target groups within the civil society, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 4. Specific messages for target groups within the civil society. Source: Authors' own work.

Category	Message
What do we offer them? Why should they be interested in the project/results? How could they benefit from the results of the project? What do we want them to do?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using the project's outcomes (and the knowledge generated in the project about biodiversity, nature-based solutions and ecosystem services) the organisations can communicate and influence decisions better about biodiversity towards their own target audience. • The project outcomes can help them to trigger transformative change. • Their biodiversity relevant communication can be stronger, sharper and more impactful. • They can improve their cooperation and engagement with their stakeholders. • They can plan and organise more impactful campaigns and do advocacy more effectively. • The project offers guidance and training to help their work to reach greater impacts for biodiversity. • They can be empowered with new knowledge of how to communicate relevant information in the best way in order to nudge and drive policy and action to halt biodiversity loss.
Relevant outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.8 – Three comprehensive guidelines tailored for enabling players (civil society, policymakers and businesses). • Trainings • WP3 outcomes, WP4 outcomes
Timeframe	From M13
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainings • Workshops • Social media • Newsletter • Media-news
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials • Guidelines • Briefs • Infographics

- Illustrated transformative change stories

4.5 Scientific Community, Researchers

The scientific community and researchers can benefit greatly from the results of the PLANET4B project. The results of the project can help advance scientific knowledge by uncovering new information about biodiversity loss and the factors that contribute to it. It can also help identify the gaps in our understanding of the topic. This can be conducive to guide future research efforts and ensure that we focus our efforts on the most important areas.

Future research projects can provide policymakers with further information they need to make informed decisions ensuring that policies continue to be based on the most recent scientific results. The project is likely to inspire researchers from different disciplines and backgrounds to collaborate contributing to the formation of interdisciplinary teams and facilitate the exchange of ideas and expertise.

Specific target groups are representatives of natural science, behavioural science, social science and gender studies focusing on intersectionality, authors of IPBES assessments and IPCC reports, science-policy interfaces (e.g. Eklipse, NetworkNature) researchers in sister projects and other Horizon Europe projects dealing with behavioural theories and transformative change.

The following table (Table 5) includes specific messages for scientific communities, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 5. Specific messages for scientific communities. Source: Authors' own work.

Category	Message
What do we offer them? Why should they be interested in the project/results? How could they benefit from the results of the project? What do we want them to do?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PLANET4B provides specific results and background from the activities to apply transdisciplinary research. • Transdisciplinary research can provide applicable knowledge for decision making relevant to biodiversity. • Transdisciplinary research has the potential to address unanswered questions in conventional scientific fields.
Relevant outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outcomes of WP1 and WP2 • Presentations on conferences, events • Scientific articles
Timeframe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Throughout the project
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media • Newsletter • Conferences, networking events with similar projects • Scientific magazines
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications • Presentations

4.6 Youth, Educators and Social Movements

To trigger transitions and transformations, the project will increase capacities of youth and education organisations by providing online training resources and guidance. To aid its application among youth groups and movements, a set of educational resources (e.g. creative exercises; interactive games to raise awareness and reflection on biodiversity) will be provided for the secondary and higher curricula as well as other extra-curricular educational settings and organisations (e.g. youth groups, movements, etc.).

Extension of materials and dissemination among schools (along with its adjustment to climate change materials) will be ensured through the consortium partner Climate Academy that directly works with schools throughout the EU. Academic partners and universities will also provide dissemination in higher education on a global scale.

Specific target groups are school networks of the EU, universities and youth movements – e.g. Fridays for Future, Youth and Environment Europe (YEE), Young Friends of the Earth.

Youth and education organisations will be addressed through the website and social media channels as well.

The following table (Table 6) includes specific messages for the youth and educators, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 6. Specific messages for the youth and educators. Source: Authors' own work.

Category	Message
<p>What do we offer them?</p> <p>Why should they be interested in the project/results?</p> <p>How could they benefit from the results of the project?</p> <p>What do we want them to do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using the project's outcomes (and the knowledge generated in the project about biodiversity, nature-based solutions and ecosystem services) the organisations can communicate and influence decisions better about biodiversity towards their own target audience. • The project outcomes can help them to trigger transformative change. • Their biodiversity relevant communication can be stronger, sharper and more impactful. • They can improve their cooperation and engagement with their stakeholders. • They can plan and organise more impactful campaigns and do advocacy more effectively. • The project offers guidance and training to help their work to reach greater impacts for biodiversity. • They can be empowered with new knowledge of how to communicate relevant information in the best way in order to nudge and drive policy and action to halt biodiversity loss.
<p>What do we offer them?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using the project outcomes, they can communicate better about biodiversity issues. • They can influence policymakers to make more effective biodiversity policy implementations.

<p>Why should they be interested in the project/results?</p> <p>How could they benefit from the results of the project?</p> <p>What do we want them to do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They can raise awareness, promote new attitudes and inspire actions of their target groups.
Relevant outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.9 – Online training and educational resources for communicating biodiversity and triggering transformative change. • D5.10 – Adjusted training materials for secondary and higher education.
Timeframe	M30–M36
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainings • Social media • Newsletter • Conferences • Meetings, bilateral consultations
Tools	Online training resources

4.7 Local Communities

Empowered communities can actively contribute to safeguarding biodiversity and implement nature-based solutions. These communities will be reached locally and through organisations like ICLEI (Local Governments for Sustainability), C40 (Cities Climate Leadership Group) or Global Covenant of Mayors.

They will be also reached through the case studies of the project with similar messages to the general public as well as locally relevant messages.

4.8 General Public

Biodiversity loss affects every aspect of our lives including our health, economy and overall well-being – communicating about the project and its results can not only increase the visibility of the project and help to disseminate its results but also raise awareness of the topic of biodiversity.

Communicating about biodiversity loss (and the importance of our decisions) to a general public is needed to sensitise the issue. This can inspire individuals and communities to take action to protect and conserve biodiversity. By educating people about the importance of biodiversity, they can be encouraged to make lifestyle changes that reduce their impact on the environment, support conservation efforts and advocate for policies that protect biodiversity.

In addition, communicating about biodiversity loss can help bridge the gap between scientists and the public. Scientific research on biodiversity loss can be complex and technical, making it difficult for non-experts to understand. By translating scientific findings into accessible language and presenting them in engaging ways, people can learn about the importance of biodiversity and the urgency of protecting it.

The general public will be informed through the project news (website and newsletter) and social media activities.

Since one of the project's main questions is how biodiversity is currently perceived, the project's findings can be used to enhance its own communication activities (EO 1 – information on relevant messages of biodiversity communication³).

The following table (Table 7) includes messages for the general public which can be fine-tuned based on the project's findings. Questions to be asked in this fine-tuning process are: Why should the general public care about the project? Why is it interesting/valuable for people? What aspect of the project can be interesting for them? (see also CBD, Global Biodiversity Outlook 5⁴ and WWF, Understanding Biodiversity Awareness in 9 countries⁵).

Table 7. Messages and examples for general public. Source: Authors' own work.

Category	Message
(The importance of) biodiversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We rely on biodiversity for our very existence. It provides us with the basic ecosystem services that allow us to survive and thrive.
Biodiversity loss, scale of the problem, consequences, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alarming and continued loss of biodiversity now threatens both the biosphere and human life because of inapt governance. Over-consumption is an important driver in biodiversity loss.
The importance of decisions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We make decisions almost every day that can affect biodiversity. We can also influence biodiversity related decisions.
The project – how it works, what solutions we plan to provide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> See section 3.1 General messages of the project.

5. Communication and Dissemination Plan

5.1 Timeline of M19–M30

All PPs are actively involved in communication and dissemination activities to achieve the expected impact of the project. By utilising the potentials of the planned channels (e.g. website, social media, newsletter, media contacts, participation in different events) and networks of the PPs, the project has the potential to multiply the effects of disseminating the project results which requires the active participation of the PPs. The distribution of communication and dissemination tasks is based on the project outputs and milestones and the agreement by the PPs (Table 8). Ensuring the highest level of credibility and competence, the communication tasks are aligned with the strengths and capacities of the partner in charge.

³ REA (2022). Grant Agreement: Project 101082212 – PLANET4B. Part B, p.5.

⁴ CBD (2020). Global Biodiversity Outlook 5. Available from <https://www.cbd.int/gbo5>. Access: April 24th, 2023.

⁵ WWF (2022). Understanding Biodiversity Awareness in 9 countries. Available from https://wwfint.awsassets.panda.org/downloads/wwf_global_biodiversity_awareness_study_2022_only_numbers.pdf. Access: April 24th, 2023.

Table 8. Overview of main communication and dissemination activities. Source: Authors' own work.

Phase	Main focus, activities, objective
Initial phase, M1–6	<p>The first phase is about kick-starting the communication and dissemination activities. The main goal is to create a solid base for the upcoming activities (visual identity, designing the website, setting up internal communication). By the end of this phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual identity (logo, branding, templates, etc.) is ready and shared with the PPs. • Website is fully operational (contents are uploaded, there is at least one news article). • Social media activities have started (few “warm-up” contents). <p>Some project meetings and presentations are organised.</p>
Operational phase, from M6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broader communication activities will start once the website is fully operational and at least one main/key deliverable is available on it. • Social media activities will be intensified, news on the project website will be published (and further disseminated via the newsletter) and meetings and workshops with key actors will be held during this period. In addition, press releases will be sent to inform the global/regional media about the project.
Maturity phase, close to the end of the project (M30–M36)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Here, the main focus is on the promotion of the concrete results, the final findings/outputs.
Additional phase, after the end of the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making sure that the outcomes are available after the project ends (activities for five years after the end of the project).

Table 9. Communication and Dissemination plan for M19–M30. Source: Authors' own work.

Communication/ Dissemination output	Tool	Action	Partner in charge	Target group	Related deliverable	Month of communication
Workshop report on theories and its implications for practice	Public report/article, brief	Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (LinkedIn, Twitter) with short explanations. News is included in the newsletter.	RU	TG4 TG3 TG5	D1.6	M19
Transdisciplinary diagnostic framework for biodiversity decision-making assessment	Public report, brief	Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (LinkedIn, Twitter) with short explanations. News is included in the newsletter.	NINA	TG1 TG3 TG4	D1.7	M19
Report on pre-test and pre-validation of contextualised intervention methods	Public report, brief	Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (LinkedIn, Twitter) with short explanations. News is included in the newsletter.	CU	TG3 TG4 TG5	D2.2	M19
Report on the system mapping and leverage points for each case	Public report, brief	Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (LinkedIn, Twitter) with short explanations. News is included in the newsletter.	CG	TG1 TG3 TG4	D3.2	M26

Communication/ Dissemination output	Tool	Action	Partner in charge	Target group	Related deliverable	Month of communication
Mapping of leverage points and transformative pathways for upscaling at the EU and global context produced for 5 sectors		Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (LinkedIn, Twitter) with short explanations. News is included in the newsletter.	CG	TG1 TG3 TG4	D4.2	M28
Project website	Project website	Project website and newsletter are promoted in the social media of the project as well as in the social media of the PPs.	GD, All PPs	All target groups	D5.4	ongoing from M7
Social media activity	Posts	Relevant social media posts are reshared by the PPs.	GD All PPs	All target groups	D5.2	ongoing from M3
Newsletter	Newsletter	Promoted on the website, in the social media and via email. PPs promote the newsletter in their channels (social media, website, network).	GD All PPs	All target groups	D5.2	M20, M26
Press releases	Press release	Promoted on the website, in the social media and media. PPs contribute to promote their own media contacts.	GD All PPs	All target groups	D5.2	M27; M30

Communication/ Dissemination output	Tool	Action	Partner in charge	Target group	Related deliverable	Month of communicat ion
Updated Synergies Strategy	Public report, brief	Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (LinkedIn, Twitter) with short explanations. News included in the newsletter.	UNEP- WCMC	TG1 TG2 TG3 TG4	D5.6.	M30
Presentations at relevant scientific conferences and events	Presentation, poster, brief, posts articles		All PPs	TG4	All deliverables	ongoing from M3
Presenting PLANET4B policy relevant outputs on relevant policy events at EU and UN levels	Presentation, brief, post, article press release		All PPs	TG1	D4.1–D4.4	ongoing from M6
PLANET4B outputs with cooperation of sister projects and other entities	Presentation, brief, post, article, press release		All PPs	TG1 TG2 TG3 TG4	All deliverables	ongoing from M3

Note: policymakers (TG1); businesses (TG2); civil society (TG3) – (a) conservation NGOs, (b) social NGOs; scientific community (TG4); local communities (TG5); youth, educators and social movements (TG6).

5.2 Project Partner's Responsibilities and Workflow

The Communication and Dissemination WP leader (GD), the contributing PPs and the project coordination team (PCT including MLU, CU, UNEP-WCMC) will work together for effective communication dissemination and exploitation of project results and outcomes.

Tasks and responsibilities of WP5 leader Good Issue (GD)

- Being responsible for the coordination and monitoring processes of Task 5.1 and Task 5.2.
- Creating and regularly revising the Communication Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy that is in line with the EU guidance⁶, compiling the updated deliverable in M18 and M35.
- Coordinating the communication and dissemination activities among the PPs.
- Based on the CDE strategy, creating an annual work plan of communication and dissemination tasks, closely linked to the defined outcomes, goals and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).
- Co-planning and monitoring PPs' communication and dissemination activities.
- Supporting and supervising of PPs' CDE related tasks.
- Managing the website and social media channels to ensure structured visibility of the outcomes.
- Providing templates and guidelines for the public communication and dissemination as well as visual identity and branding elements.
- Supporting the project outcomes through the promotion of materials and communication tools.
- Contributing to the reporting system using WP5 related outcomes.
- Organisation of regular meetings of the Communication Committee (COMCOM) with PPs to discuss all tasks, responsibilities and challenges related to communication and dissemination. The main means of internal communication between COMCOM members is email.

Responsibilities and tasks of the project coordination team (MLU, UNEP-WCMC, CU) related to CDE activities

- Keeping the WP5 leader (GD) informed about the progress of the project and the main outcomes of the discussions related to communication and dissemination activities with the Advisory Board and the European Research Executive Agency (REA) to ensure the proper update of the CDE strategy and plan daily activities. The main communication tool used for communications will be email and bilateral meetings every three months.
- Approving and reviewing the project communication deliverables and outputs.
- Participating in COMCOM meetings and updating internal project management work plan (Miro board) according to the information provided by the PPs.

⁶ European Commission (2020). H2020 Online Manual. Communicating Your Project. Available from https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm. Access: April 25th, 2023.

Responsibilities and tasks of all PPs related to CDE activities

Implementing effective, competent and reliable communication and dissemination activities – all PPs are involved in the CDE activities and contribute to reach the project level of KPIs undertaken in the Grant Agreement.

- Delegating one person per organisation to the COMCOM. The delegate takes part in the COMCOM meetings and follows the work of the COMCOM.
- Giving inputs to the communication management team (deliverables, reports, articles, photos, events, etc.) on their related activities.
- Adhering to the compulsory visibility elements according to the Grant Agreement Article 17 and the visual identity guideline provided by GD.
- Providing communication and dissemination content according to the annual CDE plan.
- Utilising their existing communication channels on local, national and transnational level (website, social media, newsletter, conferences, events, media lists, etc.) and networks (stakeholders, target groups) to promote PLANET4B's outcomes by sharing the results of the project.
- Reporting on their CDE activities regularly (every six months) following the reporting templates developed by the PCT and GD together.

6. Communication Channels and Tools

6.1 Visual Identity

The visual identity and its practical application (templates) play a critical role in communicating/disseminating the project and its results in a coherent and outstanding way. The visual identity builds on the logo and its elements (shape and colour). The appearance of the logo is simple, but strong, easy to recognise and easy to use. It refers to the name "planet" (concentric circles), biodiversity as our main topic (colours), and also evokes "action" (influence, decision, triggering change, etc. – "target" structure).

In the project's visual communication, we use the following elements: fonts, colour palette, logo, logo variations, logo elements (circular pattern), presentation, deliverable and social media post templates, photos as well as rollup.

Since it is difficult to illustrate the project's complex and abstract concepts (such as "decision making", "biodiversity related decisions", "transformative change", "biodiversity related values, behaviours and norms", etc.) in the visual communication (website, social media posts, etc.) we will use simple, general but strong pictures to accompany the project communication. These pictures are either showing

- a) positive biodiversity examples (natural forests, green scenery, animals, conservation pictures, etc.) or
- b) images about biodiversity loss.

We will avoid using staged⁷ and symbolic pictures (e.g. globe, etc. in a human hand). When using pictures with people⁸ we intend to choose an illustration that is as authentic as possible.

The visual identity is explained in the Brand Guideline, shared with the consortium. PPs will use the visual elements through their social media posts, presentation and report (deliverable) templates, etc.

Visibility and Use of Funders' Logos

PLANET4B receives EU and non-EU funds – UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) and State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) from Switzerland – for the project implementation. Pursuant to the legal agreements with the funder organisations, in any public communication and dissemination activities of the PPs, the logos and acknowledgement of funding must be indicated (see project Brand Guideline). The relevant rules are laid down in the Grant Agreement (Art. 17) and in separate agreements with UKRI and SERI.

6.2 Written Contents

Addressing the communication challenge we face (e.g. an overcrowded communication sphere), we will apply a set of rules to our written communication that are consistent with the EU communication guidelines and the latest trends in science communication. When communicating about the results of the project, it is important to use a language, a style, and an approach that is clear, concise and accessible to a wide range of an audience.

Wherever possible, in our communication we will use a clear and simple language and messages that avoid using jargon or technical terms that may be unfamiliar to non-experts. Where necessary, we will define any technical terms. We will try to avoid overly technical or complex explanations and instead focus on the description of our findings in a way that is easy to understand. By doing so, we can help ensure that the research results are understood and valued by a diverse audience, contributing to the goal of creating a greater societal impact.

6.3 Website

The PLANET4B website (<https://planet4b.eu/>) is the main interface for communication with the public and will be updated regularly. The website traffic will be monitored using Google Analytics which provides data on users and their interactions with the website.

Beyond the main function of introducing the project and the participants the website will:

⁷ A staged photograph, also known as a stock photograph, is an image that is taken with the purpose of being licensed and used in various media, such as advertisements, websites, and magazines. Photos of this kind are usually shot in a controlled environment, with models or objects carefully arranged and posed to convey a particular message or idea.

⁸ The use of photographs picturing people will always follow the principles of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of PLANET4B: it requires ethical considerations, including obtaining consent, respecting privacy, avoiding misrepresentation, respecting ownership and avoiding exploitation.

- make the results (deliverables) easily available for download and use through a clear and accessible structure;
- share news, articles, events;
- attract audience for the newsletter;
- build up trust by transparency (sharing information about the project, the participants, etc.).

The website will be operated by GD under the supervision of the PCT.

The website structure is as follows:

Main/opening (home) page

The opening page is technically a quick snapshot of the project using short information bits in a scroll-down structure. Its elements are: banner slide (3–4 moving banners; one will show a project slogan another will promote a report or an event), project description (short description with a “read more” option), latest news (2–3 of the latest or most important news), partners (logos of the PPs), “sign up for newsletter” panel, “ask the expert” panel, contact, social media icons (LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube), disclaimer/privacy policy, etc.

About

The project: a short description of the goal(s) of the project and its main activities. Partners: introduction of the PPs with a short description of the respective organisation and its role in the project. Team members: name, photo, link to LinkedIn profile.

Case studies

Collection of 11 stories (case studies). Each case study on this page will have a sub-page with the accompanying information (plus photos, videos, etc.).

Library

Project documents: all the deliverables and outputs (reports, articles, etc.) will be uploaded for download. The website uses tags for choosing between the type (report/article/brief/policy, paper/training material, etc.) as well as the topic/category of the document (communication/decision, making/transformational change, etc.) Media: newsletters, press releases, logo book.

News

News: news about the projects, its outcomes, similar projects, etc. and other related contents (interviews, blog entries, etc.). Events: participation in public events (conferences, workshops, etc.) related to the PLANET4B project; contributions of PPs (e.g. presentation, panel discussion, poster, etc.) will be promoted on the website.

Number of website visitors planned: 5.000.

Throughout the first year, the website consistently served as the primary platform for our communication activities. We have shared 11 public deliverables, accompanied by concise summary briefs, to provide clear and accessible information. During this period, the website attracted 2,800 visitors, which is over half of our target of 5,000 for the entire project lifecycle.

6.4 Social Media Channels

PLANET4B aims to have a strong presence in social media, enhancing the outreach to its target audience and the broader public. To ensure the maximum of usability and exploitation and to make the best use of the already developed social media networks of the PPs the focus has been given to those social media that PPs have been using regularly and successfully to communicate and interact with their partners and other stakeholders.

Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram and YouTube (see Table 10) have been selected as the most appropriate social networks to promote the project achievements, news and outcomes. Regarding the communication about the project and the dissemination of its results we will primarily use the project's own social media channels. While LinkedIn and Twitter are to be used to reach specific target groups, Instagram will serve as a tool to address the general public. The project's YouTube channel will function as a platform to have access to the project's video contents (e.g. videoclips from workshops).

To ensure that all relevant target groups are regularly addressed, the responsibility also lies with the PPs to make frequent use of their institutes' channels – website, newsletter and social media (see Table 11). In addition, we will build on the potentials of other projects under the Horizon Europe calls. Together with the PPs, GD will reach out to communication teams of other projects or organisations as part of Task 5.3 of WP5 in order to involve them in the planned communication activities.

Fitting into their own social media routine, PPs (as well as individuals) are also encouraged to develop their own contents – not just to repost PLANET4B news and contents but to post information on events they attended, workshops they organised or any other content relating to PLANET4B topics. Since these posts are designed to address individuals to be using a more personal tone, they can mobilise a different level of potential in the communication and dissemination activities.

PLANET4B social media links:

- <https://www.linkedin.com/in/planet4b-project/>
- <https://twitter.com/Planet4bProject>
- <https://www.instagram.com/planet4b/>
- <https://www.youtube.com/@horizoneuropeplanet4b>

Official hashtag: #PLANET4B

Other recommended hashtags: #biodiversity, #transformativechange #policy #governance #pluralvalues #intersectionality #time4betterdecisions #behaviourchange

Number of social media followers planned: 1.000.

Number of social media posts planned: 700.

Throughout the first year of the project, several pieces of content were shared regularly across the PLANET4B social media channels with two main objectives: 1) to disseminate information about the project activities, and 2) to increase our follower base.

As of now, our follower count across all platforms is approximately 400. While this is a good start, we remain committed to reaching our ultimate goal of 1,000 followers, and we recognise the need for continued efforts to grow our online community. So far, out of the targeted 700 social media posts, we have successfully published 230 with contribution of the project consortium. This leaves a significant number of posts still to be made, highlighting an area for increased activity and content generation in our future social media strategy.

Our current follower count stands at:

- LinkedIn: 116 connections
- Instagram: 126 followers
- Twitter: 161 followers

The number of followers and activities in social media is growing dynamically throughout the project. We expect further growth in the 3rd year, when the main scientific results and policy recommendations will be published.

Our analysis indicates that LinkedIn emerged as the most effective platform. On average, our posts received 5–10 likes each, with popular posts achieving 1–3 shares. The most engaging content on LinkedIn, receiving over 20 likes, featured people involved in project activities, such as workshops and training sessions. The most liked post showcased a training session, attracting 29 likes. However, overall engagement on LinkedIn has been modest, with only a couple of comments and shares mostly limited to the more popular content.

Instagram ranked as our second most popular platform, following similar trends. Posts featuring people – from researchers to training participants, in group work settings or group photos – tended to receive higher engagement, with the most popular post about a workshop garnering 15 likes. Like LinkedIn, the number of comments on Instagram was low, totalling 2.

Twitter appeared to be the least popular platform in terms of engagement, with the highest-liked post receiving only 10 likes and a maximum of 2–3 reposts. These insights will guide our strategies for the upcoming year, as we continue to refine our approach to social media engagement and content creation, aiming for higher interaction and outreach.

Based on the feedback of our project partners, we have identified several areas for improvement in our social media engagement strategies. These suggestions are aimed at enhancing interaction, increasing reach, and fostering a more active and participatory community among our stakeholders.

Key Suggestions for Enhancing Social Media Engagement

Increasing Partner Participation:

- By heightened tagging of partner and other organisations involved in our project in social media posts, we might be able to raise even more awareness amongst the partners and foster engagement.

- Creative recognition strategies, such as highlighting actively engaged partners or creating internal awards for contributions, could be implemented to encourage further participation.
- Promoting personal stories and career insights of project members could help us create a more personal connection with our audience.

Content Creation and Diversity:

- Further encouraging partners to create and share their own content related to the project could enrich our social media presence with diverse perspectives and experiences.
- Providing partners with social media templates and even more support in content development might assist those who are less experienced with social media.
- Employing further a variety of content types, such as infographics and videos, could enhance engagement with different audience segments.
- Extending our social media post calendar for regular contributions from partners might streamline our content distribution.

Effective Use of Platforms:

- Tailoring even more content specifically for each social media platform, like polls, might increase interaction and relevance.
- Leveraging LinkedIn's strength in engaging specific target groups, and Instagram's appeal to the general public could optimise our platform usage.
- Increasing Twitter engagement through even more frequent and relevant posts could improve our presence on this platform.

Cross-Promotion and Collaboration:

- Initiating more extensive cross-promotion by sharing and reposting content from partner organisations and sister projects could amplify our reach and impact.
- More widely collaborating with the communication teams of partner institutions might lead to a more coordinated and effective promotion strategy.
- Seeking further opportunities for joint communication initiatives with other projects and organisations might expand our network and influence.

Responsive and Interactive Engagement:

- Creating an environment that encourages replies, comments, and discussions could make our social media channels more interactive and engaging.
- Implementing interactive elements like Q&A sessions might actively involve our audience and foster a sense of community.

Targeting and Reaching Broader Audiences:

- Further fine-tuning and understanding the target groups for each social media platform could help us tailor our content more effectively.
- Utilising insights from analytics to refine our content strategies might enable us to reach broader audiences, including key stakeholders and the general public.

Other Concrete Ideas We Plan to Implement for Enhanced Visibility

To further increase our visibility and engagement, we plan to introduce several unique and creative tools.

YouTube Playlists for Educational Outreach: we will create a curated playlist on YouTube specifically tailored for researchers and those interested in biodiversity, featuring songs related to nature and biodiversity. This playlist will serve as an engaging tool to draw connections between art and science.

Educational Resources for Diverse Audiences: alongside the music playlist, we will develop additional playlists, including explainer videos designed for children and a collection of biodiversity-related documentaries available on YouTube. These resources would aim to educate and inspire a broad audience about the importance of biodiversity.

Creative Campaign Visuals: to build our follower base, we will regularly post innovative biodiversity content, utilising creative campaign visuals from organisations like WWF and Greenpeace. These posts are intended to capture attention and convey powerful conservation messages.

Engaging Community Posts: we will implement regular "reminder" posts that summarise recent activities ("What happened this month?") and preview upcoming events ("What's next for the project?"). These posts will keep our followers informed and engaged with the project's progress and future plans.

Personal Engagement Through Researcher Spotlights: we plan to introduce a series of posts under the theme "What are you working on?" These posts will feature individual researchers, highlighting their current projects and the human side of scientific research. This approach aims to create a personal connection between our researchers and our audience, making the research more relatable and accessible.

By considering these suggestions, we aim to create a more engaging and dynamic social media presence, effectively sharing the project's results and activities, and building a community around the PLANET4B project.

Table 10. PLANET4B relevant platforms and contents. Source: Authors' own work.

Platform	Content
Social media of PLANET4B (Twitter/X, LinkedIn, Instagram)	Sharing different contents (see the post types below)
Social media of PPs (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram)	Sharing the main project news/results by <ul style="list-style-type: none">• reposting the PLANET4B's social media contents• developing their own contents (attending events, etc.)
Social media of PPs' individuals (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram)	Sharing the main project news/results, short news about meetings, events, etc. but also personal insights by <ul style="list-style-type: none">• reposting the PLANET4B's social media contents• creating their own contents

Table 11. Existing social media channels of the PPs Source: Authors' own work.

PP	LinkedIn	Twitter/X	Instagram	YouTube	Facebook
MLU	26k	12.2k	17.1k	3.36k	31k
MLU/SLEG Lab	5	-	-	-	-
NINA	7k	1258	2380	7.36k	13k
CU	248k	73.6k	49.1k	17.8k	195k
CU/CAWR	2 k	2.5k	-	-	2.5K
UNEP-WCMC	58k	21.6k	-	-	70k
CGE	0,2 k	170	1.3k	20	3.8k
CAC	-	-	400	-	-
DC	-	-	800	-	2.4k
FUG	-	-	-	-	600
CG	17	750	300	84	2.2k
ESSRG	1k	200	-	175	-
IFZ	67	600	500	-	-
GD	-	-	-	-	250
OOF	6	48.7k	308k	5.2k	237k
RU	167k	30.8k	27.7k	6.9k	44k
FIBL	14k	5.9k	-	-	7k
UNIFI	135k	19.5k	34.3k	6k	70k

Post types:

- News about deliverables (short summary, keywords, background, importance, link, etc.)
- Promoting short interviews of key persons/partner organisations
- Introducing partner organisations (their role, etc.)
- Upcoming events, conferences
- Upcoming workshops (promotion of workshops)
- Promoting sister project(s)
- News outside of the project
- Promoting the newsletter
- Promoting the “Ask the Expert” option
- Posts on Instagram about successful diversity campaigns and visuals (UN, WWF, Greenpeace, etc.)

The visuals accompanying the posts are produced by GD using project branded Canva templates. If necessary, the editable visuals will also be shared with the PPs to make their own posts.

Quick social media guideline

Below we provide some guidance for PPs about how to use social media:

- Use a language/tone that fits your audience. You could ask them a question or use a quote or a set of emojis and encourage them to comment under your post and share their experience.
- Use appropriate language and tone when posting on social media. Avoid using overly technical language or jargon.
- Make it clear that you are affiliated with a particular institution or organisation. This can help to establish your credibility and avoid confusion about your role and authority.
- Avoid discussing controversial topics that are unrelated to your research. This can help to avoid potential conflicts and ensure that your social media presence remains professional.
- Use multimedia content: visual communication is a very important aspect of all social media channels. Images, videos, infographics, factoids, quotes, etc. catch the user’s attention much faster and effectively than text on its own. This kind of content can easily be used to tell a story and helps to engage the audience emotionally. You can use the PLANET4B social media templates in Canva.
- When posting graphs use a clear title that briefly explains the findings. Keep graphs simple (under about 10 data points). This may mean highlighting just a portion of a graph or data from the report.
- When writing a post on social media try to keep the number of words around 10–20 (posting with photo) and 30–40 words (posting without photo). Word count includes all words (dates, names, sources, etc. – everything).

Consider the platform you are posting on and the norms and expectations of that platform carefully. For example, Twitter has a character limit, while LinkedIn is more focused on professional networking.

For more tips: “Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects”.⁹

6.5 Newsletter

PLANET4B e-Newsletters will be released every six months, offering the project community an overview of the latest project activities and developments. E-Newsletters will be both uploaded on the project website and distributed to a list of recipients. The newsletter aims to enable the subscribers to get first-hand information about the project and other projects related to PLANET4B as well as relevant and important news about our main topics. The first newsletter will be released once the website is launched.

The newsletter will be created through MailChimp, a web-based email marketing service. It will be distributed to a mailing list containing subscriber information gathered through a sign-up form on the website. PPs may also promote the newsletter through their channels. An unsubscribe/opt-out link will be available as per EU directive 2002/58/EC.

GD coordinates the editing of the newsletter. A mailing template was designed for this purpose. The sender is a dedicated email: info@planet4b.eu.

For the promotion of the newsletter, the following channels will be used:

- Social media posts
- Website
- Channels of the PPs’ institutes (website, social media channels, newsletters, events, etc.)
- Direct email (when contacting a target group, a line should be added to the email about subscribing to the newsletter)

6.6 Briefs

One-page summaries (creative briefs) will be created of each deliverable enabling results relevant to enabling players. These short briefs will be based on the deliverable, using its relevant sections (executive summary, key findings, etc.) and any additional information provided by the author(s) of the deliverable. All briefs will also be uploaded on the website.

The briefs will be prepared by the Task leads and edited by GD.

6.7 Press Releases

To further promote the project and its results, press releases will be created by GD when major project news such as policy recommendations or substantial project results are to be communicated to a wider audience. A press release will be prepared and shared with major European news organisations such as EurActiv, Politico, Policy

⁹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (2020). H2020 Programme. Guidance Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf. Access: April 25th, 2023.

Review, Reuters and other pan-European news agencies (other examples: ESG Today, Sustain Europe).

Depending on the relevance, PPs will also translate and share information with their own national, regional or local media contacts (both specialised and professional contacts). All press releases will be uploaded on the website as well.

PPs will translate and set the press release (provided by GD) to their cultural context and will disseminate it through their media contacts.

Number of planned press releases sent: 5.

6.8 Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Scientific publications represent an important means of project result dissemination. We expect that five scientific papers will be published, targeting academics, researchers and relevant professionals. Non-scientific publications have the potential to reach a wider, general and professional audience.

Scientific publications will be written (and sent/uploaded to the scientific sites/magazines) by the PPs, non-scientific publications will be written by the PPs, edited and shared by GD.

Interviews (opinions) of experts within the partner organisations will also be created, attracting media attention on the specific topics.

Guidelines (know-how) on:

- Scientific articles:
<https://www.european-science.org/how-to-write-a-scientific-article/>
- Popular science articles:
<https://royalsociety.org/blog/2017/08/writing-popular-science-as-a-scientist/>

Number of scientific articles planned: 5.

Number of non-scientific articles planned: 30.

6.9 Emails

One of the primary means of stakeholder outreach in PLANET4B will be one-on-one email to inform interested parties about project results, events and activities. We will also use emails to distribute our newsletter to stakeholders drawing attention to the project's highlights. Emails will allow PPs to conduct a small-scale targeted outreach with a more personal rhetoric; however, while email is a simple form of communication, it can be difficult to strategically plan and measure its effectiveness.

6.10 Open-Source Platforms

The project's key deliverables and relevant open access data will also be shared on open-source platforms such as OER Commons, OpenSDG, Zenodo and OpenAIRE.

6.11 Events

PPs will disseminate deliverables by participating in national and international scientific conferences as well as international EU policy and business events in order to further promote the project and engage other stakeholders while raising awareness of the PLANET4B activities and expected results. The PPs will represent the consortium and attend debates, lead debates, deliver project-related speeches, contact stakeholders and/or carry out workshops.

PPs should inform the PCT as well as the communication team about their contribution before attending events. After the event, PPs should share the material communicated (e.g. presentation) with any other relevant information so the communication team can create content (news, posts, etc.) about it.

To enable the tracking of relevant events including scientific conferences and policy events, (channelling outcomes to accelerate change) a database was created and featured on the internal communication platform on SharePoint as part of Task 5.4 of WP5.

6.12 Consultations

Key enabling players (mostly EU and UN decision-makers, business representatives, civil society members, relevant EU and global projects and initiatives) will be contacted and informed about the project and its results through bilateral in-person or electronic consultations. Additionally, through WP3 and its series of learning communities, local level stakeholders will be regularly consulted.

Stories of transformative change from the case studies' relevant places and sectors and economic value chains will be compiled. Transformation pathways will be produced. These outputs of PLANET4B as well as relevant interventions will be discussed with key enabling players among the target audience in order to enable upscaling at EU and global levels through these consultations.

Number of planned consultations: 10.

6.13 Other Visual Tools

Accompanying the promotion of the different outputs, simple but creative infographics will be created by GD. The PPs are also encouraged to develop infographics (and other similar visuals) using their own resources to aid their reports or social media activities. The production of these visual tools will be coordinated and guided by GD.

Supporting the final results of the project, videoclips will be developed under the supervision of GD. Slightly edited, short (few minutes) versions of the workshop recordings will also be made available on the website.

6.14 Media Relations

Apart from the press releases, PPs will share information about the results of the projects through their own existing media relations in order to generate TV and radio presence in the local/regional media. GD will oversee the coordination of these activities.

7. Synergies and Accelerating Changes

7.1 The Synergies Strategy

To maximise the project's impact, synergies with other relevant Horizon Europe and non-Horizon projects and initiatives are mapped, connection and cooperation are established, and joint work and outputs (e.g. press releases, posts, events) are initiated under Task 5.3 (Mapping synergies and creating cooperation with existing initiatives and projects) of WP5. The main dissemination tools of the project will be continuously worked on and reflected in line with the target groups and the mapping and synergies seeking activities.

The Synergies Strategy (D5.5) outlines how collaboration with external projects and initiatives whose areas of work have synergies with PLANET4B will take place. In this strategy, different types of collaborations are defined, types of projects and initiatives to collaborate with are outlined as well as a timeline for collaboration. This includes a seven-step process (identifying, assessing, contacting, coordinating and implementing, communicating, monitoring, setting future collaboration) detailing how to work with external partners based on the identified synergies. Therefore, the primary focus of the Synergies Strategy is to act as an internal guidance document for PPs. An initial database of over 70 EU and international projects and initiatives that are synergistic with PLANET4B has already been created (see in D5.5) and will be updated on a rolling basis."

An updated version of the Synergy Strategy (D5.6) will be produced and shared in Month 30. The process to develop the updated Synergy Strategy will involve reviewing all the collaborative activities that have happened between PLANET4B partners and external projects during M6 – M30, based on what PLANET4B partners have reported. In case of instances where not all collaborative activities were reported by PLANET4B partners, UNEP-WCMC will request the partners to provide additional detail on the collaborative activity that took place. Once this information has been gathered, a summary of the collaborative activities will be described in the updated Synergy Strategy, along with a description of what the outcomes and impacts of those collaborations have been, as well as recommendations for how PLANET4B partners can carry those collaborations forwards in the future. This information will be useful for guiding the partners to prioritise those collaborations that can produce the most impactful outcomes in terms of disseminating the work and findings of the PLANET4B project.

7.2 Channelling outcomes to accelerate change

The aim of Task 5.4 is to communicate and disseminate the work and deliverables of PLANET4B through participation at national and international events, conferences and forums where there are opportunities to engage with audiences from the public sector, research communities, civil society and private sector. In order to ensure that these activities happen in a coordinated and impactful manner, UNEP-WCMC will develop a template for partners to fill out at the planning stages in the lead up to the event (capturing succinct information on what the event is about and who the main audience is). Using this information, UNEP-WCMC will coordinate with the partner and WP5 leader Good Issue to identify and prioritise the most relevant information, messages

and deliverables to disseminate at the event, based on the subject focus and audiences for the event. After the event has taken place, partners will be asked to provide a brief summary of the outcomes of the event (e.g. what information and deliverables were disseminated and to whom, how our participation contributed to PLANET4B's work and deliverables feeding into other areas of work and research etc). Collecting information from partners about how they have disseminated PLANET4B's work at external events in a timely manner will be critical for making sure this information is being systematically collected, since it will form the basis of "Report on Accelerating Change Activities", due in M36. PLANET4B partners will be informed and reminded about the process for planning and recording event-related dissemination activities during WP leads meetings, communications meetings, and consortium meetings.

8. Capacity Building for Enabling Players

The Task 5.5 Enhancing the capacity of enabling players and change agents to initiate transformative change will be led by CU; participants: CAC, CGE, UNEP-WCMC, MLU, RU, CG) (M30–M36).

Building on outcomes of WP1 and WP4 three practical guidelines for three target groups (civil society, policymakers and businesses) will be developed to provide detail on potential transformative pathways, intersectionality context, behaviour and creative methods and communication tips on biodiversity (D5.8).

An online training programme and educational resources (D5.5.2) will be developed to involve all these materials for the target groups to aid biodiversity prioritisation. With specific extensions, the educational resources will also be tailored for both secondary and higher education curricula (D5.9, D5.10).

Although the final materials (D5.8, D5.9., D5.10) will be published in the last phase of the project (M33, M36), preparatory work will start earlier.

9. Internal Communication

The purpose of the internal communication section is to ensure that the external communication tasks are carried out as efficiently as possible by all the consortium members. Furthermore, it aims to make communication and dissemination workflow (tasks, responsibilities, monitoring) transparent.

9.1. Internal Communication Rules and Tools

Planning and Management Tools

The basic tools that will be used during the project to accomplish the planning and carrying out of communication and dissemination activities among the PPs are:

- Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy and plan: This document contains the main goals, tools and responsibilities on CDE activities of the consortium with key messages, main actors, channels and specific activities, timeline and KPIs. The document is renewed every six months.

- The project management work plan (Miro board): Miro board that contains all the PLANET4B activities, CDE activities and outcomes (deliverables, KPIs, milestones) as a detailed work plan of the consortium.
- COMCOM meeting: The Communication Committee (COMCOM) members meet online bi-monthly to share and discuss CDE related issues, refresh the project management work plan regarding CDE related tasks as well as prepare the renewing of the CDE plan.

Internal Communication Tools

The main tools of internal communication:

- Regular emails
- COMCOM, periodic meetings (online bi-monthly)
- WP leads meetings (online every four months)
- Steering Committee meetings (annually)

Intranet – SharePoint/Teams

For now, the PLANET4B project's main internal documentation and information sharing platform SharePoint/Teams is provided by CU. SharePoint/Teams is open for all PPs. This private tool will enhance the information exchange among all PPs (minutes, internal documents, WP's specific information, etc.) as well as facilitate internal coordination. The related communication and dissemination documents and plans can be found under the WP5 folder.

10. Exploitation

The European Commission describes exploitation as “the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.”¹⁰

Exploitation is the effective use of project results through scientific, economic, political or societal routes of utilisation. The objective of exploitation is to go one step further than dissemination and turn research and innovation actions into concrete value and impact for society. Thus, the main audience of exploitation is the same with the one suitable for dissemination.

PLANET4B will aid the exploitation of the results through three fundamental steps.

- 1) Producing a thorough and reflective CDE plan that will continuously be updated to reflect on the exploitation opportunities of the project outcomes. The plan will include exact steps to identify the key exploitable results, their potential platforms and future users, IPR strategy, specific plans for each key exploitable result by the consortium and relevant PPs that will also include potential integration and funding opportunities for the continuation and sustainability of the results.

¹⁰European Commission (2023). EU Grants. AGA – Annotated Grant Agreement. EU Funding Programmes 2021–2027. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf. Access: April 25th, 2023.

- 2) Generating a visually appealing, user-friendly, relevant and easily findable resources portfolio devised specifically for each target group. Securing the retained relevance of materials over time, ensuring their attractiveness and easy-to-use structures along with an easily navigable website structure and search option; SEO (Search Engine Optimization) will ensure that the resources will be available even after the project's timeline.
- 3) Ensuring that availability and cross-linking of materials are not only operational through PLANET4B's and the PPs' websites but through the Science Service, KCB, BISE, Oppla, Eklipse platforms, along with websites and social media channels on current and upcoming Horizon Europe projects under the same and relevant calls as well as other open-access channels (e.g. Open SDG platform). To further support dissemination and exploitation, open access EU services will be explored – Open Research Europe, Horizon Results Platform (HRP), Horizon Results Booster, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and CORDIS.

Intellectual property rights

Within the EU funded R&I-projects, several complementary partners from research, small and large industry come together. Therefore, it is important to set common grounds and learn about each other's expectations, aims and needs early on. Exploitation workshops within COMCOM meetings will help to clearly define the key exploitable results, characterise and prioritise them jointly with the PPs. Exploitable results can be of scientific or commercial relevance and may be either published or protected.

Intellectual property (IP) includes:

- Products of the mind
- Products of research and experimentation
- Products of creativity
- Intellectual property, like physical property, can be a valuable asset.
- Physical property and intellectual property as an asset which can be traded (sold, bought, leased, used as collateral or donated)

Intellectual property rights (IPR)

The law provides legal rights to protect your intellectual property, known as intellectual property rights (IPRs):

- Patents (technical inventions)
- Copyright (software, written works, engineering drawings, semiconductor topologies, etc.)
- Design rights (appearance)
- Database rights (creation and arrangement of data)
- Trademarks (utility models/petty patents, etc.)

11. Monitoring Results

In order to achieve the successful implementation of CDE activities and fulfilment of the relevant objectives and KPIs (Table 12), a systematic monitoring will be carried out throughout the project implementation. The monitoring will be performed internally on an annual basis and will be officially reported in the relevant deliverables. Regular monitoring will allow the identification of possible risks and deviations from the CDE objectives and performance indicators and the timely planning of any necessary corrections and actions to address potential implementation problems. Such an approach will improve the overall performance of the relevant activities and enable a more efficient evaluation.

An online form has been created for reporting all CDE activities PPs are performing. The form is available on SharePoint/Teams to all PPs. Specific CDE and WP5 relevant templates are created for monitoring purposes and will be sent out to request data on a six-month basis from all PPs.

Online presence of PLANET4B will be monitored using specific analytics monitoring software, i.e. Google Analytics as well as relevant social media analytics (number, age, source, distribution, location of the visitors on website, number of posts, followers of the project's social media profiles or views of YouTube videos).

Table 12. Key Performance Indicators. Source: GA, data provided by PPs, and Authors' data collection.

Tools	KPI	Target	Mid-term results¹¹
Website	No. of visitors	5.000	2.800
Newsletter	No. of subscribers	200	63
Social media	No. of followers	1.000	403
	No. of posts	700	230
Videos, illustrations and artwork	No. of videos produced	10	0
	No. of target groups reached	500	0
Infographics	No. of infographics	5	0
	No. of target groups reached	500	n.a.
Press release	No. of press releases sent	5	1
Non-scientific articles (e.g. The Conversation), radio and TV interviews	No. of articles	30	11
	No. of radio interviews	5	1
	No. of TV interviews, spots	2	0
	No. of people reached	100.000	n.a.
Scientific publications	No. of publications	5	8 in preparation
Workshops for enabling players and stakeholders	No. of workshops organised	64	63
	No. of participants	200	
Consultations	No. of consultations	10	2
Joint actions with other EU projects (e.g. joint event, joint communication)	No. of actions	10	5
Presentations at scientific conferences and events	No. of presentations	5	21
Public deliverables	No. of deliverables	28	11
Deliverable briefs (a creative, short version of the main messages)	No. of briefs	25	8
Online training	No. of online trainings	1	0
	No. of target group participants	300	
	No. of education institutes/youth groups reached	100	

¹¹ Figures reflect the status of mid-April 2024.